

ID 1370

EFFECTS OF MATRIX PLASTIC PROPERTIES ON STRESS TRANSFER AND TENSILE STRENGTH OF GLASS FIBRE/EPOXY RESIN UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

F. M. ZHAO^{1,2}, T. OKABE², F. R. JONES¹ and N. TAKEDA²

¹*Department of Engineering Materials, University of Sheffield, Sheffield, S1 3DJ, England*

²*Graduate School of Frontier Sciences, University of Tokyo, Tokyo 153-8904, Japan*

ABSTRACT: The results of fragmentation testing show that the plastic properties of resin have a large influence on the stress transferred between glass fibre and epoxy resin and the mode of micro-damage. It was found that an increase in the tensile yield stress of the matrix results in a decrease of the fragment length and a change in the micro-damage at a broken fibre. The results from tensile tests of unidirectional (UD) composite indicate that the tensile strength of the UD composites increases with increasing tensile yield stress of the matrix when the micro-damage at the broken fibres is interfacial debonding. The theoretical results show that the resin matrix can provide high shear stress to cause further fragmentation of fibre and to influence the tensile strength of the UD composite.

KEYWORDS: Stress Transfer, Interface, Matrix Plastic Properties, Tensile Strength, Unidirectional Glass/Epoxy Composite

INTRODUCTION

The fragmentation test of single fibre composites (SFC) is one of main micro-mechanical methods to evaluate the interfacial properties between fibre and polymer matrix. This method is used widely since the fibre stress state in SFC specimen is somewhat similar to in the real unidirectional composites [1]. The reported results have indicated that the fragmentation behaviour of the fibre embedded in the matrix depends not only upon the interfacial property [2,3] but also the statistical fibre strength [3,4] as well as the matrix properties [5,6,7,8].

FEM analysis and birefringence patterns have shown the local matrix yield around the broken fibre [2,9]. The attention has been focused on the effect of the yield properties of the matrix on stress transfer and SFC test in recent researches [2,4-6]. Tripathi *et al.* [2] and Rechar *et al.* [6] investigated the stress transfer using finite element analysis taking account of the matrix plastic behaviour. Huang and Young [10] studied the interfacial shear stress and fibre stress distributions for fragmentation test of carbon fibre using laser Raman spectroscopy. In the studies, the resin matrix shows plastic behaviour with cold drawing after yielding. In a recent study, Zhao *et al.* [5] examined the fragmentation of glass filament embedded in the epoxy matrix without yield and cold draw. The result indicates that an increase in the tensile stress of the matrix results in a decrease of the fragment length and a change of the micro-damage at a broken fibre.

The effect of the stress transfer on the tensile strength of UD glass/epoxy composites has been examined by Zhao *et al.* [11,12] The results showed that the stress transfer and micro-damage have a synergistic influence on tensile strength of the composite. The proper adhesion of fibre and matrix can offer a balance of elastic and strength properties as well as fracture and failure characteristics for a composite. In order to ensure rational design for interfacial properties, the role of plastic properties of resin matrix on stress transfer and tensile strength of UD composites must be understood.

In the present study, the stress transfer and micro-damage at the different interfaces of glass fibres in epoxy matrix were studied by fragmentation of a single embedded filament. The

effect of the interfacial conditions and matrix properties on the tensile strength of UD composite was examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of curing agents, triethylenetetramine (TETA) and m-phenylenediamine (mPDA), were used for curing Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (Epikote 828, Yuka-Shell Company). TETA and mPDA were supplied by Yuka-Shell Company, Japan and Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd, Japan. Respectively. TETA and mPDA were used in 11 wt% and 13 wt% of resin, respectively. Curing temperature and procedure are 50 °C/80 min and 100 °C/60 min for Epikote 828-TETA, and 75 °C/120 min and 125 °C/120 min for Epikote 828-mPDA. The cured resin shows typical mechanical characteristics of a highly cross-linked resin: without yield point and cold drawing when resin specimens failed at about 7–8 % applied strain.

E-glass rovings with fibre diameter of 13 µm were used. As-received water-sized fibres (2500 filaments/bundle) were unsized and untreated, which were supplied by Nippon Glass Ltd. The water-sized fibre was treated using γ -glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane (γ -GPS) or γ -methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (γ -MPS) in the laboratory. γ -GPS (S510) and γ -MPS (A174) were supplied by Chisso Company, Japan and Nippon Unicar Co. Ltd, respectively. The concentrations of the solution are 0.5 wt% for both γ -GPS and γ -MPS. The detailed surface treatment of the glass fibre was reported in elsewhere [11].

Single filaments were extracted at random from the rovings with the same surface treatments as UD composites and mounted on a polytetrafluoroethylene mould for preparing SFC specimens. The resin, mixed with the hardening agent, was poured into the mould where a single glass filament was supported. The dimensions of the mould were: 1.4 mm thickness, 3 mm width, and 18–20 mm gauge length. The fragmentation tests of SFC were performed at a strain rate of 0.0015 min⁻¹ and a load cell of 2 kN was used.

Unidirectional composites have same interface condition as in single fibre composites. Fiber volume fraction was about 54.2%. Axial tensile tests of UD composites were carried out at 0.24 mm min⁻¹ using a testing machine (EHF-EB5 SERVOPULSER) with hydraulic grips. More than five specimens for each kind of fibre surface treatment were used.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fragmentation tests

The results from fragmentation tests are summarised in Table 1. Since the saturation was not reached with the TETA cured resin, the average fragment length was measured at the same applied strain for comparison in all specimens. In the Epikote 828-TETA resin (resin A), it is notable that for γ -GPS and γ -MPS treated fibres, number of fibre-breaks is almost same at the same load. Therefore, their average fragment lengths are approximately equal as shown in

Table 1 Average fragment length, interfacial shear strength and Weibull parameters of fibre strength

Surface treatments	Average fragment length (µm)	Debonding length (µm)	s_{fi} at 10 mm (MPa)	Weibull modulus	Maximum shear stress at interface (MPa)
Epikote 828/TETA					
γ -GPS	332	0	1844	6.27	44.5
γ -MPS	338	32	1680	6.34	39.5
Epikote 828/mPDA					
γ -GPS	250	29	1844	6.27	58.1
γ -MPS	304	54	1680	6.34	48.2

Table 1. This suggests that the interface of fibre/ γ -MPS/Epikote 828-TETA provides a similar stress transfer function as γ -GPS-treated fibre. But in the Epikote 828-mPDA resin (resin B), the average fragment lengths decrease approximately by 25% and 10% for γ -GPS and γ -MPS treated fibres, respectively. The results suggest that stress transfer effectively increases. This indicates that the properties of resin matrix have a large influence on stress transfer. It is expected that this will increase the tensile strength of unidirectional composite. Maximum shear stress at the interface was determined according to the Kelly-Tyson model assuming critical fibre length to be $4l/3$ [13,14]. It is seen from Table 1 that the γ -GPS treated fibre has the maximum value and thus its interfacial adhesion is the strongest.

It was observed that the micro-damages at the end of broken fibres with different surface treatments differ. In the Epikote 828-TETA resin, it has been found that when the fibre breaks only matrix cracking occurred for γ -GPS-treated fibre. For γ -MPS-treated fibre, interfacial debonding and matrix cracking took place simultaneously.

In the Epikote 828-mPDA resin, interfacial debonding was observed for both fibres. For γ -GPS treated fibre, although a combination of matrix cracking and interfacial debonding occurred, the dominant mechanism was still matrix cracking. It has been found in a previous study that the interface debonding is related to both the level of the interfacial adhesion and yield shear stress of resin matrix [5]. The change in damage mode from matrix cracking to debonding suggests that the resin matrix with the higher yield strength can provide a larger shear stress [5], which leads to the debonding at the end of the broken fibre and causes further fragmentation of fibre.

Results of tensile tests of UD composites

The tensile strength of UD glass/Epikote 828-TETA composites with two fibres is shown in Figure 1. It is noted that the tensile strength reaches a maximum value for γ -MPS treated fibre that does not have the strongest interfacial adhesion. For UD composite with γ -GPS treated fibre, the tensile strength was about 10% lower than that with γ -MPS, although its interfacial adhesion is the strongest. The results indicate the stronger interface adhesion cannot offer necessarily higher tensile strength for unidirectional composite. If failure strain is considered, the maximum is also reached for γ -MPS. This suggests that the interface/interphase with γ -MPS is tougher than that with γ -GPS fibre in the Epikote 828-TETA.

Figure 1 Tensile strength of UD composite with γ -GPS and γ -MPS treated fibres in Epikote 828/TETA (resin A) and Epikote 828/mPDA (resin B)

It is seen from Fig 1 that the maximum tensile strength was also obtained for γ -MPS treated fibre in Epikote 828-mPDA. Thus the tensile strength of composites with γ -MPS was about

21% higher than that with γ -GPS. The strength of composite from γ -GPS treated fibre was identical to that with Epikote 828-TETA.

It is found that the UTS for γ -MPS treated fibre/Epikote 828-mPDA increases approximately by 8% and fracture strain increases approximately by 12%, compared with Epikote 828-TETA. These may be attributed to higher stress transfer efficiency in Epikote 828-mPDA as shown in the results in SFC.

THEORY

Elasto-plastic shear-lag model of single fibre composite

An elastoplastic shear-lag model incorporating local matrix plasticity has been recently developed to obtain the tensile stress and shear stress distributions along the fibre fragment and the interface [15]. A cylindrical model of a half fragment length was used including fibre, resin matrix, and interphase. The matrix and interphase are assumed to obey the elasto-plastic stress-strain relation and the fibre is elastic. E^e and E^p are Young's and plastic tangent moduli of matrix and interfacial region, as shown in Fig. 2, and G is the shear modulus of matrix. Two plastic behaviours of epoxy matrix, perfectly plastic as well as without yield point and cold draw, are considered to compare their effect on shear stress at interface and tensile stress in fibre. Thus yield strain of matrix, e_{ny} , was determined in the way shown in Fig. 2. The yield stress of matrix, s_{ny} , is given by the von-Mises relation. The superscripts m and f denote matrix and fibre. E_f is Young's modulus of fibre. Radius of the fibre and interfacial region are r and $r+R$, respectively. The cylindrical model is then divided into k elements and each node is called, in turn, $i = 0, 1, \dots, k$ as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 2 Schematic of stress-strain curve of matrix

Figure 3 Schematic of analytical model

The shear-lag equations for matrix elements and interface elements are divided into two regions. One is the region where the stress is transferred by the elastic interfacial shear stress, and the other is the plastic region where the stress is transferred by shear yield stress. Then, the shear-lag equations for matrix elements are divided into four regions because matrix itself will be yielded at the higher strain and thus it should be considered whether the interfacial

shear region is elastic or the plastic, and matrix is elastic or plastic. The nodal displacements for fibre and matrix, u_i^f and u_i^m , can be numerically obtained, thus the element stresses are given with the obtained displacements by

(Fiber)

$$\mathbf{s}^f = \frac{E^f (u_i^f - u_{i-1}^f)}{\Delta y} \quad (1)$$

(Matrix: Elastic)

$$\mathbf{s}^m = \frac{E^e (u_i^m - u_{i-1}^m)}{\Delta y} \quad (2)$$

(Matrix: Plastic)

$$\mathbf{s}^m = E^p \left(\frac{u_i^m - u_{i-1}^m}{\Delta y} - \mathbf{e}_{my} \right) + \mathbf{s}_{my} \quad (3)$$

(Interphase: Elastic)

$$\mathbf{t} = G \frac{u_i^m - u_i^f}{R} \quad (4)$$

(Interphase: Plastic)

$$\mathbf{t} = \left[\frac{2(E^e - E^p)}{E^e E^p} + \frac{1}{G} \right] \left(\frac{u_i^m - u_i^f}{R} + \frac{2\sqrt{3}(E^e - E^p)}{E^e E^p} \mathbf{s}_{my} \right) \quad (5)$$

The properties of fibre and resin matrix are summarised in Table 1 and 2 for calculation. Figure 4 shows the shear stress distribution based on the property of matrix B and only considering the matrix crack at the fibre end. It is seen that for the resin with perfectly plastic deformation, there is a constant shear at the region near fibre end, which is close to yield shear stress of resin matrix, while for the resin without yield and cold draw, the maximum shear stress occurs at the fibre end. This affects the tensile stress in fibre, and thus a relative quick increase in tensile stress is achieved. Similarly, the calculated result indicates that the resin B can provide a larger shear stress than the resin A, and thus tensile stress in fibre increases quickly. This can explain the experimental results from the fragmentation, e.g. shorter fragment and debonding occurred in resin B.

Table 2 Mechanical properties of resin matrix and glass fibre

	Elastic modulus E^e (GPa)	Plastic modulus E^p (GPa)	tangent Poisson ratio	Tensile yield stress (MPa)
Resin A (Epikote 828/TETA)	3.4	0.58	0.35	69
Resin B (Epikote 828/mPDA)	3.2	0.79	0.38	75
E-glass fibre	72		0.25	

Figure 4 Interfacial shear stress distribution and fibre tensile stress distribution for matrix with perfectly plastic deformation and plastic deformation without yield

Prediction of tensile strength of UD composites based on a 3D model

Okabe *et al* [15] have developed a three dimensional shear lag model to predict the tensile strength of unidirectional polymer matrix composite. The model is based on the shear-lag model by Hedgepeth and Dyke [17]. The effect of matrix plastic properties and statistical characteristic of fibre was incorporated into the present model. The model composite is composed of tension-carrying fibres connected by a resin matrix which carries only shear. A square fibre distribution was considered. The sizes of the three dimensional model for calculation were 30 mm long in length, 2 mm wide in width and height. The fibre volume fraction was 54.2 %.

It is assumed that resin matrix obeys the von Mises's yield criterion. The Weibull parameters of γ -MPS treated fibre, scale parameter of 1550 MPa, and shape parameter of 6.34 for a fibre gauge length of 24 mm, were used for calculation. The predicted strength as a function of matrix yield stress is shown in Figure 5. It is seen that the tensile strength of composite increases with increasing matrix yield stress. This is similar to those calculated by Mahiou and Beakou [18]. The calculated results agree well with the measured results.

Fig. 5 Predicted tensile strength of UD composite as a function of matrix yield stress

For γ -GPS fibre composites, the predicted strength is higher than measured one, by 18% for resin A and 11% for resin B, respectively. The prediction is quite satisfactory compared with the reported result [19]. The predicted stress-strain curve of UD composite for γ -MPS-treated fibre agrees well with the measured curve as shown in Fig. 6. For γ -GPS fibre composites, the discrepancy between the model prediction and experiment is higher than those with γ -MPS fibre. The higher predicted values are due to the fact that the micro-damage at broken fibres is matrix cracking and the composite failure is matrix-controlled.

Figure 6 Predicted and measured stress-strain curves for γ -MPS treated fibre/resin B UD composites

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the plastic properties of resin matrix on stress transfer, micro-damage and tensile strength of UD composite has been examined. It was found that an increase in the tensile yield stress of the matrix results in a decrease of the fragment length and a change of the micro-damage at a broken fibre. The tensile strength of glass fiber/epoxy UD composites increases with increasing the tensile yield stress of resin matrix when the micro-damage at broken fibre is interfacial debonding. The calculated results from elastoplastic shear-lag model show that the resin matrix can provide high shear stress to cause further fragmentation of fibre. The prediction from a 3D strength model shows that the yield stress of matrix has an influence to the tensile strength of the UD composite.

REFERENCES

1. Herrera-Franco, P.J. and Drzal, L.T., *Composites*, 1990. Vol. 23, 2.
2. Tripathi, D., Chen, F. P. and Jones, F. R., *Proc. R. Soc. Lon.*, 1996. Vol. A452, 621.
3. Zhao, F. M., Okabe, T. and Takeda, N., *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, 2000. Vol. 60, 1965.
4. Deng, S.Q., Ye, L., Mai, Y.W. and Liu, H.Y., *Composite*, 1998. Vol. 29A, 423.
5. Zhao, F. M., Okabe, T. and Takeda, submitted to *Composites Interface*
6. Lane R., Hayes S.A. and Jones F.R., *Composites Interface*, 1999. Vol 6, 425.
7. Drzal, L.T., *Mater. Sci. Engng.* 1990. Vol. A126, 289.

8. Netravali, A.N., Henstenburg, R.B., Phoenix, S.L. and Schwartz, P., *Polym. Compo.*, 1989. Vol. 10, 226.
9. Bascon, W.D. and Jensen, R.M., *J Adhesion*, 1986. Vol. 19, 219.
10. Huang, Y. and Young, R.J., *Composites*, 1995. Vol. 26, 541.
11. Zhao, F.M. and Takeda, N., *Composites*, 2000. Vol. 31, 1203.
12. Zhao, F.M, Takeda, N. and Jones, F.R, *Proc.6th DCF*, Manchester, 2001.
13. Kelly, A. and Tyson, W.R, *J Mech. Phys. Solid*, 1965. Vol. 13, 329.
14. Ohsawa, T., Nakayama, A., Miwa, M. and Hasegawa, A., *J Applied Polymer Sci*, 1978. Vol. 22, 3203.
15. Okabe, T. and Takeda, N., *Proc. 9th US-Japan Conf. Comp. Mater.*, Ed. Fukuda, H., Ishikawa, T. and Kogo, Y., Mishime, Japan, 2000.7 pp879-886.
16. Okabe, T., Kamoshita, K. and Takeda, N, submitted for publication.
17. Hedgepeth, J.M. and Dyke, P.V., *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1967. Vol. 1, 396.
18. Mahiou, H. and Beakou, A., *Composites Sci and Technol*. 1997. Vol. 57, 1661.
19. Rosen, B. W., *AIAA J.*, 1964. Vol.183, 1985.